

The Localization of Open Educational Resources: The role of culture, user and activity

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Abstract. In this article we argue that Open Educational Resources (OER) provide avenues for a more seamless exchange and localization of valuable content for educational use. But instructional design must be adapted to consider the process of remix and reuse which needs to take place for OER to benefit users worldwide. This paper argues that instructional designers interested in creating or adapting open materials must begin with the “event” or “activity” as a focal point in the development of educational resources.

Resumo. Neste artigo, argumentamos que Recursos Educacionais Abertos proporcionam maiores oportunidades para a troca e localização de conteúdo para uso educacional. Mas o design instrucional precisar ser adaptado para que *remix* e reuso possa beneficiar usuários ao redor do planeta. Este artigo argumenta que designers instrucionais interessados na criação e adaptação de recursos abertos devem começar com o “evento” ou “atividade” como ponto focal no desenvolvimento de recursos educacionais.

Introduction

Since the coining of the term “Open Educational Resources” (OER) in 2002 the movement has gained substantial momentum (UNESCO, 2002). Millions of dollars have been used to promote the production and research around OER, especially by foundations (West & Victor, 2011) but governments as well (CERI, 2007).

There are expectations that OER can promote a new, distributed model for higher education (Taylor, 2007); that open formats and licenses will encourage a more liberal exchange of resources; that new models for the production and dissemination of resources will emerge, among others. Importantly, it is believed that OER can encourage teachers and students to become producers of content rather than just consumers of prepackaged materials (Rossini, 2010). These and other possibilities make OER an exciting field of inquiry for those involved in educational change and innovation (see, Plotkin, 2010).

In this article we argue that OER will suffer from the same limitations faced in the past by educational innovations if the issues of context and culture are not taken into consideration. We examine OER from the perspective of cultural barriers, particularly within the universe of online content. It is argued that access and use of OER is limited not only by the well known limitations learned through research into the digital divide, but also suffer from serious cultural constraints which are largely unaddressed.

In order to discuss this intersection between design, culture, education, and resources, it is assumed that in instructional design a particular standpoint on culture must be taken (Amiel, Squires, & Orey, 2009). Negating the neutral grounds with which “school” and “cultural groups” are often proposed is of particular importance here. In order to do so I must therefore argue from a particular standpoint. I take the case of Brazil, particularly in the context of K-12 public schooling. From this argument I hope the reader will be able to interpret,

filter, accept or dispense with the arguments based on comparison with the context and situation to which she might be faced. I begin with the example of textbooks in Brazil as a case for the potential benefits of OER. Next I discuss a series of concerns around access and participation in online environments. Finally I discuss the relationship between instructional design and OER, and propose a framework based on activity or “event” in order to consider culture in the instructional design of OER.

Educational Resources and Context

Public school students in Brazil receive a printed textbook for all areas of knowledge from 1st through 8th grade. The National Textbook Program (PNLD; *Programa Nacional do Livro Didático*) is one the largest federal textbook distribution program in the world. It has had particular impact in providing a minimum set of educational resources to students and teachers in isolated and/or poor communities (Correios, n.d.). In 2009 alone, the Federal government spent R\$330 million reais in book purchases (MEC, 2009a). Between one fifth and one third of the annual production of books is made of government-purchased textbooks, corresponding to over 30% of publisher’s profits. Approximately 75% of all PNLD purchases are made from four major publishing houses (“Maior segmento do mercado editorial é o de livros didáticos,” 2007; Ortellado, 2009). The program is complemented by a similar initiative focused on high school, which began in 2004 (PNLEM; *Programa Nacional do Livro Didático para o Ensino Médio*). Costs for the program, not counting distribution of the resources was R\$416,9 million in 2008 alone (MEC, 2009b). This initiative is complemented by other book ‘kits’ (MEC, 2009c).

Books are commissioned and approved by the federal Ministry of Education. Once analyzed for their physical resistance and appropriateness, and rated on the quality of their content, teachers receive a book-guide and a menu from which to choose from. Though free to choose, publishing houses heavily advertise and

promote their textbooks at the local level. Importantly, the federal government purchases the physical entities, but never the content itself. Therefore, every three years books are re-purchased in full and the sums transferred to publishers (and/or authors) who remain copyright holders of the published materials.

In São Paulo, the PNLD is complemented by a statewide program that distributes textbooks to teachers (CP; *Caderno do Professor*) and students (CA; *Caderno do Aluno*)¹. The textbooks cover the statewide curriculum and are closely aligned to an annual evaluation (SARESP; *São Paulo State Evaluation of School Performance*) conducted at years 2, 4, 6, 8 and last year of high school focused on the subjects of Portuguese, Mathematics and Science. These are then connected to bonus and incentive schemes for school personnel (Oliveira, 2009). The increasingly strong ties between curricula, materials, accountability measures in the form of student-exams, and financial incentives, have lead to substantial dependence on the official books as a source of both curriculum and content to be covered in these specific areas of knowledge, a trend which is similar to recent developments in the United States (Ravitch, 2010).

At the same time, modern discourse directed at educators and parents often emphasizes the incredible wealth of information available online to which students and teachers now have access to enrich their classroom experience. In this article we focus more specifically on the context of a traditional school, where a teacher is able to select educational resources based on personal preference, teaching style, knowledge of student-audience, and other factors. Initiatives focused on the K-12 level propose a series of challenges not only to the traditional textbook but also to teacher and student roles which are quite different from higher education, for example.

The role of the traditional designer has shifted even within the more traditional realm of public schooling. Schools in Brazil have depended (and most

1 Other resources are also distributed, such as a guide focused on the administrators (*Cadernos do Gestor*)

still do) on the distribution of books by the Federal and State governments. But gaps do exist, and new designers of educational resources have begun to penetrate the walls of schools. Teachers who share their resources (using portals such as the *Portal do Professor* sponsored by the Ministry of Education) are effectively *designers* sharing their resources. The community at large has also become a class of designers, insofar as individuals and groups begin to produce quality educational material (for example, Khan Academy or Wikipedia). Even the traditional textbook has become flexible and open to customization by a user-cum-designer. Textbooks can now be purchased from traditional publishers in customized formats², or from upcoming publishers in very flexible formats (see for example, the publishing company Flat World Knowledge). This shift towards customization stems from recognizing that the audience can indeed be part of the design process. This also means that users, such as teachers, should be able to tailor resources to their needs, rather than adapting their needs (or objectives) to existing resources. While access to these resources is largely through digital formats, the principles behind them pose interesting challenges to the production and dissemination of print materials as they point to new models encouraging choice, print-on-demand, and alternative instructional design (such as modularity).

Whichever the case, this is a far cry from choosing a single textbook to be used for a period of three years with three different groups of students, from a menu offered by the federal government for use in *all states* of the federation; or at a more localized level, making use of a small set of textbooks in more than 5000 high schools across the state of São Paulo.

New media, technology, and the school

It is now a cliché that the Internet has changed how education is operating

2 See for example Pearson's "Custom Library" at <http://www.pearsoncustomlibrary.com> or Wiley's "Custom Select" at <http://customselect.wiley.com>

and will operate in the near and distant future. A large section of these expectations is directed towards the use of the plethora of digital materials available on the Internet in order to enrich and modify current educational practices, both in formal and informal contexts, from pre-school to post-graduate education. This truism, unfortunately, is the offspring of historical expectations towards the power of educational change that can be fostered by technological tools. Without an explanation of constraints and context, the power of technology to change education seems feasible and tangible. Despite increasing availability of computer and laptops, the challenges to accessing and making use of these equipments are systemic and have been well documented in Brazil and elsewhere with remarkable symmetry. These include the difficulty in transferring knowledge about home use to pedagogical use of technical artifacts; a lack of interest by some teachers, lack or diminished access to resources and infra-structure; lack of support and maintenance; tenuous guidelines for equipment use, among others (Amiel, 2006; Bueno, 2001; Cysneiros, 2001; Cysneiros, 2003). There is ample evidence that unless a comprehensive, long-term, and holistic approach to technology integration is taken, there will only be sporadic successes and general disappointment even in the most innovative projects (Severin & Capota, 2011).

As a recent example, high schools in the state of São Paulo are generally equipped with a state-sponsored 'kit': a functioning computer laboratory with approximately 15-20 computers, with Internet access and regional support by 1-2 trained students who offer support (the program is termed "Acessa São Paulo"). Repeating previous findings in the literature, access to the Internet is intermittent and unavailable for long periods of time, and student monitors are not always available, rendering the space unusable or problematic (Amiel & Morceli, 2007).

The Internet does indeed provide a variety of tools and content, but as we know from 20-odd years of research into the digital divide, it provides only for some. The examples above are part of a larger phenomenon – the assumption by

more affluent groups that *everyone* is connected. Recent statistics indicate that 65 out of 100 Europeans have access to the Internet, which is the highest ratio worldwide, and that roughly 1/3 of the world population is connected (ITU, 2010). But we also know that usage can mean many things, including a range of devices with varying capabilities and connection quality. We also know that many other factors determine the actual usage of Internet services based on the network of people and things that are at play in a particular event (Amiel, 2006; Lima & Brown, 2007; Strover, 2003). We therefore continue to live in a paradox. The provision of information and communication technologies (ICTs) in the form of hardware and infrastructure continues to proliferate inside and outside of school. Internet access through these devices follows the trend (NIC.Br, 2010). However, the problems in making these developments associate themselves with school improvement and participation remains illusive.

Participation

Once one has reasonable access to the Internet, what does it take to create and contribute? Warschauer (2002) has proposed that this divide is better thought through the framework of “social inclusion” which expands beyond concerns over equipment and infrastructure:

“There is not one type of ICT access, but many; the meaning and value of access varies in particular social context; access exists in gradations, rather than in a bipolar opposition; computer and Internet use bring no automatic benefit outside of particular functions; ICT use is a social practice involving access to physical artifacts, content, skills, and social support; and, acquisition of ICT access is a matter not only of education, but also of power.”

Perhaps the greatest initial barrier to making use and contributing online are the linguistic constraints to the web-based experience. In a three set approach to

international interface usability, Nielsen (1996) proposes that language is the first and foremost element one should examine. An interface must be able to display the users' language, character set, and notations; and the interface and documentation must be usable and understandable in the users' language as well³.

Estimating the linguistic diversity of the online environment is quite difficult. The most reliable study using a complex search of terms employing particular search engines indicated that in 2007, for every 100 pages in English on the web, there were approximately 8,5 in Spanish, 10 in French, 6 in Italian, and 3 in Portuguese (Pimienta, Prado, & Blanco, 2009). The authors point to some interesting factors affecting linguistic diversity online. First, the presence of English online, though significant, hovers around 45-50% and not a substantial majority as anecdotal evidence will have it (and perhaps even less, considering the percentage of Internet users). Second, increasing the access of native speakers of a particular language to the Internet naturally leads to an increase of language-presence. Third, early adopters of Internet-access technologies tend to be consumers of content and only later, producers (DeGennaro, 2008). There is therefore an undetermined delay between providing access and expecting content on a specific language to increase, which has particular implications for poorer countries. Finally, since English is considered a *lingua franca*, many linguistic groups feed content in English online either as their *online* language, or as a second language (translation) of content in the native tongue (Pimienta et al., 2009). By this and other studies and methods, content in Portuguese online does not surpass the 5% mark (Pimienta et al., 2009; UNESCO, 2005). Language has become an issue of access. The translation of materials has become the final effort in many educational projects aimed at promoting open educational resources⁴. While translation does indeed help increase there is much

3 The third and part in this three-pronged approach is that a system must “match the user's cultural characteristics”, a concept we will discuss futher.

4 A high-profile example is the translation of MIT's OpenCourseWare materials to multiple

to be done in order to promote the OER agenda, and to provide access to quality educational resources to people around the world.

Digital educational resources

Initial optimism regarding digital learning objects⁵ would have us believe that only a small number of resources would suffice to quench the thirst for knowledge. Downes' (2001)⁶ position illustrates this best when he said that "...the world does not need thousands of similar descriptions of sine wave functions available online. Rather, what the world needs is one, or maybe a dozen at most, descriptions of sine wave functions available online." This is also defensible from a financial perspective:

"It makes no financial sense to spend millions of dollars producing multiple versions of similar learning objects when single versions of the same objects could be shared at a much lower cost per institution."
(Downes, 2001, p. 2)

If the percentages for language presence on the web hold, and dozen learning objects were created to explain mathematical concepts, Portuguese speakers would stop at the first and barely learn addition⁷.

languages.

- 5 In the context of the original article it was used to describe small simulations such as "sine wave functions" but we can extrapolate it to consider a more open definition, including most digital content (images, audio, video and text) for the purposes of the argument.
- 6 This was an early position, and I'm unsure if Downes has changed it or, likely, enriched it with further arguments. It is used to illustrate a perspective that is still endemic.
- 7 We have only recently begun to (partially and insufficiently) address some of these concerns through just-in-time translation (as those available in search engines) and user generated content (as in *Universal Subtitles*). Translation is only a limited tool, with substantial human, resource, and financial constraints.

An attention to multilingual content is not only a question of human rights guaranteed by the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (Particularly article XXVII; (United Nations, n.d.) but also as a way to assure that the people around the world can learn from and contribute to an open web, and as an important tool in the preservation of material and immaterial culture and educational opportunities (UNESCO, 2003). Indeed we do need multiple version of very different content to satisfy the multitude of languages, contexts, and activities to which people belong and engage in, even if they do originate from a single set of five-star materials as has been done to Massachusetts Institute of Technology's (MIT) OpenCourseWare (OCW) materials, translated to Portuguese⁸, among others languages. This is indeed an unlikely and mostly undesirable case, as it discourages development of local production and voice, and in last instance re-create old colonialist attitudes, a point made by OECD (Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development; CERI, 2007).

The issues of language provide a strong example supporting the need to think about educational resources beyond the purpose representing those who are "different", or being "tolerant" of minority perspectives (Sleeter & Grant, 1994). A more appropriate objective is that of integrating content and perspectives, and promoting insights into how knowledge is constructed (Banks, 2004) which can only happen when we empower users who constitute these minorities.

Designing to promote access

This theme has begun to attract substantial attention within the OER movement, which has attracted a vibrant and diverse community of people involved in all areas of education from around the world. There is now substantial concern in regards to how these educational resources can be adapted and modified to satisfy the linguistic and cultural concerns of end-users, a non-trivial

8 See <http://mit.universia.com.br/sobreocw.jsp>

process (Lin & Lee, 2007). Thomas, Mitchell, & Joseph (2002) have argued that:

“...historically many professionals in the field of Instructional Technology have taken a culturally neutral position in the creation of instructional products. By not directly addressing culture in the design of instruction, many products have been designed that inadequately address the needs of the population for whom the instruction was designed. Unintended consequences of this shortcoming include the production of ineffective instructional products, the under use of potentially effective products, culturally insensitive products, and products that are deemed overtly culturally offensive by some members of certain populations.” (p. 40).

Indeed there is limited discussion on the topic of culture within the texts focused on the design of instructional materials, and courses on instructional design (ID) do not often make reference to the topic. Thomas and colleagues propose that the traditional model for instructional design, ADDIE⁹, must be complemented by elements of interaction (collaborative/participatory design), introspection (reflective practice), and intention to assist in a culturally-aware design that permeates all phases of the project. Following this rationale Amiel, Squires, and Orey (2009) systematized three design schemes or scenarios for a more culturally-aware design of open educational resources. The three schemes are, essentially:

1. Incrementing resources to include cultural introspection in the form of resources which discuss and complement the resource itself
2. Promoting participatory design with end users and a varied development group

⁹ Focuses on five linear steps: Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluation, though many alternative models have been developed based on these five elements (Gustafson & Branch, 2002)

3. Creating technically flexible resources that can be customized at point-of-use

These recommendations are useful to begin thinking about the possibilities for adaption of open resources, a technically more open production of materials, and the localization of existing materials by local producers. But how does this play out outside of the realm and resources of traditional instructional design? Specifically, how would design look like if focused on cultural concerns in complex scenarios like those in public schools classrooms? What “culture” are we addressing when we address “cultural” concerns?

Culture for design

Fortunately or not, definitions of the concept of *culture* abound. If taken within the monocultural perspective, the teaching of culture in the classroom focuses on the customs, festivities, and languages of particular “others,” generally groups of people from different nations or ethnic groups. A monocultural perspective tends to imply that the group one belongs to is comprised of a single dimension of culture everyone can identify with, such as “American”. Little attention is paid to the diversity evident on individuals, even in a small community. Bullivant (1986) offers a wider definition of culture which highlights its fluidity and its constant struggle to adapt and persist:

“...the generalized composite of interdependent and valued traditional and current public knowledge and conceptions, embodied in behaviours and artifacts, and transmitted to present and new members, both symbolically and non-symbolically, which a society has evolved historically and progressively modifies and augments, to give meaning to and cope with its definitions of present and future existential problems” (p. 42).

Proposing multiculturalism is not simply to recognize different ethnic groups such as Latinos, Jews, or African Americans. Multiculturalism examines

group identities (ethnicity, nationality, race) but necessarily highlights the individual, proposing “[a] focus away from the surface, outward aspects of culture and points our attention to the deep structure of culture, to people’s beliefs and understanding of the world” (Noel, 2000, p. 3). It recognizes the many latent identities of every individual. Identifying a “Latino” community can serve as a useful construct in some circumstances, but presupposes a homogeneity that does not exist and often undermines substantial differences. Latinos diverge in national origin, religion, values, traditions, attitudes and beliefs. An individual could spend a lifetime examining *all* sources of identity, but exploring a gamma of individual characteristics provides a far better account of the “self” and others than a single label such as “Latino” could possibly provide.

Still, complex definitions of culture might be instructive, but pose a serious challenge to the designer of instructional resources. Considering that one must be introspective about culture in the process of design, such definitions provide little in terms of guidelines. Defining the learner becomes a difficult task for the designer or teacher:

"Although no one will disagree with the statement that human beings differ, the question of what makes differences into cultural differences is not easy to tackle. If two students, one from Latin America and one from North America, perceive the interpersonal behaviour of their teacher differently we are inclined to label these differences as cultural... However, if two students from the same country perceive teacher behaviour in different ways, we will explain these differences as determined by personal preference or character." (Oord, 2005, p.180)

A common approach to creating “world-ready” materials is to generalize characteristics of particular groups according to a wide-angle view of culture (Hoft, 1996). Hoft presents a series of popular segmentation schemes focused on “cultural variables”. These include the well-known scales proposed by Hofstede

to distinguish the people of different countries: power distance, individualism, masculinity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term orientation. These wide segmentation schemes are useful when generalization and expedience is of utmost importance, but many times they simply do not hold in specific scenarios (Rebolledo-Méndez, Orey, & Alvarez-Rodriguez, 2011). More localized approaches have been advocated at least in the sphere of formal schooling. These include having deeper and more consistent understanding of the history and struggles of particular ethnic groups (Banks, 2000). Another proposes a better understanding of how students view their “cultural pie” (Noel, 2000). In this case, a teacher could ask students to identify membership to different groups. A student might identify herself as partially by nationality (Brazilian), but also ethnically (say, Latino, if living in the United States), but also as a parent, footballer, or other memberships which constitute *affinity groups* (Gee, 2007).

This reflection points us to how the now well-established idea that a culture is not just composed of groups of exotic folks in a far away land, but affinity groups which share particular plans, symbols, routines, beliefs. Designing for affinity groups is a far more complicated task. Let us contrast two strategies, within a particular context of application: a group of 35 students (a class) in a public high school in the State of São Paulo, Brazil. If considering the cultural adaptation of educational resources, the teacher might use her knowledge of the class as a whole to adapt or create a set of materials that correspond to the audience at hand. A general audience analysis might yield a series of generalized constructs: these students are at a poor neighborhood, in the periphery of a large urban area, with low reading comprehension and writing skills, and mostly from evangelical Christian families. One could go on, but these elements provide enough generalized “cultural” knowledge to modify or direct the design. In contrast, should the teacher attempt to identify the affinity groups with which students identify themselves, she could begin by using the cultural pie example outlined above. The resulting cultural analysis would prove to be far more chaotic. Students might be evangelical Christians but perhaps with contradictory

practices and beliefs (most certainly contradicting what a general construct ‘evangelical Christian’ might provide). They might see themselves as living in a relatively “good” neighborhood, contradicting assumptions of negativity towards their socio-economic status. The analysis of these cultural pies might lead to student and teacher awareness of class diversity (which is good, and is its main purpose), but in assisting the teacher in the design of educational materials, the compounding intersections of affinity groups would not result in useful guidelines for the designer of instructional materials.

The challenge is thus: if we design according to a general segmentation scheme such as described above we risk reaching inadequate assumptions regarding a student population. It will also configure practice that is distant from the way a teacher would operate in “intuitively” analyzing a student group. Local cultural analysis of affinity groups is a reasonable activity to conduct, say, during a first week of class. It does a better job of providing an understanding of how students themselves understand to what groups they belong. In either case, generalization from data is essential, but in the second a student-generated conception of affinity is used to create a basis from which to generalize.

An activity

While the approximation to student-generated data provides a better lens, the use of this data is likely an elusive task. An alternative is to look at culture from the perspective of an *activity*. When people exercise a particular practice, within a particular affinity group, there are certain routines, behaviors, ideas and rules (implicit or explicit) that are at play. These semiotic domains (Gee, 2007) are different for a student investigating chemical bonds in a chemistry course and a student learning poetry from a literary group. Learning these codes and practices are part of what makes a physicist, a poet, or a footballer. At the bottom of these semiotic domains, are particular sets of activities that take place. At every activity students engage particular skills and concepts, which derive from affinity groups to which they belong (or belonged to in the past).

At the heart of this argument is the degree to which a cultural determinant or a “structure” imposes particular patterns of action. This of course does not play out in actual events. Individuals do not have complete cultural-autonomy in order to negate their historicity. Sahlins (2000) examines this tension from the perspective of a historical “event”¹⁰, concluding:

“The structures interact in the medium of people’s projects. According to the nature and manner of the interaction, local structures can restrain, intensify, orient, and otherwise direct the development of larger historical forces” (italics in the original, p. 343).

Another, more closely related lens to the nature of the event is that presented by *activity theory*. Here one presupposes that subjects and objects do not exist before engagement in an actual event (activity). This enigmatic phrase proposes that in the design of instructional projects, it is better to think of the student through the activity which will take place rather than to begin with the analysis of the characteristic of the group itself. In other words, students never bring their complete arsenal of cultural habits to bear on every activity that takes place. As humans, we come to select appropriate behaviors, routines and actions based on particular practices, in an adaptive and non-determinant fashion. A Brazilian student might well fall within Hofstede’s description that Brazilian society does not readily accept change and is very risk adverse in a particular domain and activity, but this risk aversion might completely disappear within another domain of activity. Similarly, students who identify themselves as evangelical Christians might as well engage their beliefs when discussing issues of abortion but might not do so when discussing relationships. The contingencies of an activity mediate the sort of cultural determinants which will come into play, not only because of the diversity which exists in a particular individual, but

10 Sahlins context is that of war and struggle in the Fijian islands, but the relationship between cultural “structure” and people’s “events” are, I believe, transferable to this context.

because of the collective characteristics of the individuals which make up a unique cultural group at *each activity*. As Sun (2006) contents: "...we should move toward designing local technology with rich understandings of use activities in context instead of simply applying cultural conventions to localization work" (18).

Instructional systems design models which propose circular or iterative processes of analysis and design, to provide space for such introspection. As such we agree with Thomas and colleagues (Thomas, Mitchell, & Joseph, 2002) that culture has been a neglected component of instructional systems design. Though it might not be explicit as part of an audience analysis phase, there is clearly room for methods of elicitation and investigation of cultural makeup to be included in existing instructional design methods. What is called for is not so much a transformation of existing models, but for an inclusion of techniques and processes that can make interaction possible. We suggest that the nature of the activity itself be an orienting or focal point to instructional design. This is particularly important when trying to consider how a different cultural group will engage with instructional materials. Focusing on activity rather than on the cultural "structure" helps the designer avoid the pitfalls of structure-as-determinant-of-event, cultural generalizations and stereotypes which do not materialize in the individual, and ignoring the true diversity of affinity groups that each individual is composed of.

We have recently begun examining this perspective in the collaborative design of activities (lessons) for high school sociology (Pezzo, Amorim, & Amiel, 2011). Through school visits and interviews, pertinent contextual elements including resources, preferences, student groups and characteristics and other relevant instructional elements are elicited. An iterative process of instructional design is done in collaboration with the teacher in order to arrive at an instructional piece that is aligned with the cultural configuration at hand. While this might not be an thrifty process, it does provide valuable insights into the differences that exist between pre-conceptions based on stratifications schemes

and specific groups as unique cultural configurations based on specific events (like a lesson on sociology).

Conclusion

In this article I discussed how OER can be used to think about an instructional design that considers context and cultural concerns. I began by proposing examining the issues of schooling, access and participation to defend the idea of OER as a viable movement, but also to highlight some of the concerns related to the discourse around remix and reuse. Finally, I presented an alternative to cultural segmentation as a way to analyze culture in design of OER. The present work reaffirms the importance of open licenses and formats as an essential starting point in supporting local remix and reuse.

The concept of activity as the focus of design has been elaborated elsewhere and frameworks for investigation of activities exist (Kaptelinin & Nardi, 2006). There is a need to extend these analyses into instructional design frameworks and bring these discussions into the field of OER. These are important tasks that will remain for further study and discussion.

Open Educational Resources provide an excellent platform for the exchange of educational materials around the globe. As designers of new resources, or *remixers* attempting to benefit from the plethora of materials available, designers must focus on adapting these materials to activities, events and the people and artifacts, which constitute local action. This mindset is quite different from what occurs currently within a publishing and design environment that encourages 'built it and they will come (or buy)'. As design become more distributed and participatory, new opportunities will arise to make great resources even better by adapting them to the activities, people, and resources of a particular event – but this can only occur within a design framework which considers adaptation, localization, and remix a standard practice, not an afterthought.

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